

Studies in the Cyclohexane Series. Part XIII. : Synthesis of Some Substituted 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-acridones and phenanthridones and *N*-Aryl-5-methyl 2,3,4,5,6,7-hexahydroindol-2-ones

H. S. BAJAJ, R. D. DESAI and G. S. SAHARIA

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110007

Manuscript received 28 November 1974 ; revised 2 April 1975 ; accepted 29 April 1975

Ethyl 4-methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate is condensed with a number of primary aromatic amines at room temperature and 180°-190° to give anils and anilides, which on cyclisation furnish substituted 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-acridones and -phenanthridones.

4-Methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-acetic acid is also condensed with a number of primary aromatic amines to give *N*-aryl-5-methyl-2,3,4,5,6,7-hexahydroindol-2-ones.

THE condensation of ethyl cyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate with aniline at room temperature and primary aromatic amines at high temperature and the subsequent cyclisation of the anilides, obtained in the latter reaction to tetrahydrophenanthridones has been reported¹. Later primary aromatic amines were condensed with ethyl cyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate at room temperature and the products of reaction on cyclisation furnished tetrahydroacridones². These workers have also reported the preparation of some acridones by the condensation of 2-, and 4-methylcyclohexanones and trans- β -decalone with anthranilic acid. It was, therefore, thought of interest to study this reaction with β -keto esters of substituted cyclohexanones and compare their behaviour with those of 5-, 6-, 7- and 8-membered analogues³⁻⁷ during the course of this reaction.

Thus, ethyl 4-methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate was separately condensed with aniline, 3, 4-dimethylaniline, 2, 4-dimethylaniline, *o*- and *p*-chloroanilines, 2, 4-dichloroaniline, *p*-bromoaniline, α - and β -naphthylamines, *p*-nitroaniline, *o*- and *p*-phenetidines, *p*-toluidine and *o*- and *p*-anisidines in presence of glacial acetic acid and the reaction mixture on keeping for two weeks at room temperature gave anils (I) which gave no colour reaction with aqueous ferric chloride. When heated at 240-250° (I) cyclised to give the corresponding 3-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroacridones (II).

Similarly, ethyl 4-methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate was condensed with *m*-toluidine, 2, 5-dichloroaniline and other bases when anilides(III) were obtained. These gave a positive test for the enolic function with aqueous ferric chloride confirming the structure III. All these anilides except that from *p*-nitroaniline (which decomposed) cyclised to the corresponding 2-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydrophenanthridones (IV) when heated with PPA.

γ -Keto acids and their esters react with arylamines at high temperature to give heterocyclic compounds⁸⁻¹¹ and the condensation of cyclohexan-1-one-2-acetic acid¹² with primary arylamines has been reported. 1-Aryl-2-oxo-2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7-hexahydroindoles (V ; $n=4$) so obtained when hydrogenated in presence of Adam's catalyst gave the corresponding 1-aryl-2-oxo-octahydroindoles (VI ; $n=4$).

4-Methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-acetic acid (VII) on condensation with aniline, *p*-toluidine, 2, 4-xylidene, *o*-chloroaniline, α -naphthylamine, *o*-anisidine and *o*- and *p*-phenetidines at 200°-20° gave *N*-aryl-5-methyl-2,3,4,5,6,7-hexahydroindol-2-ones (VIII). Structures assigned to these products are confirmed by elemental analysis and IR spectral data.

From these studies it is concluded that the substituted cyclohexane ring is more reactive as compared

to simple cyclohexane or its lower and higher homologues since ethyl 4-methyl-1-anilino/arylaminocyclohex-1-ene-2-carboxylates (I) were cyclised by heating for 6-15 min at 240°-50° while longer periods of heating were required for cyclohexane or its lower and higher analogues.

Experimental

Substituted 1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroacridones

Ethyl 4-methyl-1-anilino-cyclohex-ene-2-carboxylate.

A mixture ethyl 4-methylcyclohex-1-ene-2-carboxylate (1.84 g; 0.01 mol), aniline (0.93 g; 0.01 mol) and a drop of glacial acetic acid was stored over potassium hydroxide in a desiccator for two weeks. The reaction product on fractionation gave ethyl 4-methyl-1-anilino-cyclohex-1-ene-2-carboxylate at 172°/3 mm. $n_D^{20.5}$ 1.5758 (Yield : 1.6 g ; 61.8%).

(Found : C, 74.0 ; H, 7.8. $C_{16}H_{21}O_2N$ requires C, 74.1 ; H, 8.1%) IR γ_{max}^{Neat} 1650 cm^{-1} (NH bending).

Other aryl aminoesters prepared in an analogous manner are entered in Table 1.

Ethyl 4-methyl-1-anilino-cyclohex-1-ene-2-carboxylate (1.3 g) was heated at 240-50° (oil bath) for 6 min and the product on crystallisation from benzene-acetic acid gave 3-methyl 1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroacridone m. p. >300°. (Yield : 0.7 g ; 65. 7%). IR γ_{max}^{Nujol} 1639 cm^{-1} (>C=O of γ -hydridone).

All the other acridones prepared in the same way are given in Table 2.

TABLE 1—ETHYL 4-METHYL 1-ARYLAMINOCYCLOHEX-1-ENE-2-CARBOXYLATES

Arylamine	b.p./m.p. °C	Yield %	Ref. index	Molecular formula	Analysis			
					Found C	% H	Requires C	% H
1. <i>p</i> -Toluidine	185/1.5 mm	73.3	$n_D^{20.5}$ 1.5720	$C_{17}H_{23}O_2N$	75.5	8.3	74.7	8.4
2. 3,4-Dimethylaniline	190/1.5 mm	73.2	$n_D^{20.5}$ 1.5725	$C_{18}H_{25}O_2N$	75.0	8.6	75.3	8.7
3. 2,4- "	174/1.0 mm	69.7	$n_D^{20.5}$ 1.5635	"	75.1	8.6	"	"
4. <i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	183/1.0 mm	85.2	n_D^{20} 1.5835	$C_{16}H_{20}O_2NCl$	65.3	6.8	65.4	6.8
5. <i>p</i> - "	m. p. 49	73.3	—	"	65.3	6.7	"	"
6. 2,4-dichloroaniline	167/1.5 mm	76.2	—	$C_{16}H_{19}O_2NCl_2$	58.4	5.6	58.5	5.8
7. α -Naphthylamine	195/1.5 mm	84.1	—	$C_{20}H_{28}O_2N$	77.4	7.3	77.7	7.4
8. β - "	215/1.0 mm	68.0	—	"	77.5	7.5	"	"
9. <i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	m. p. 156	82.2	—	$C_{16}H_{20}O_4N_2$	63.0	6.5	63.2	6.6
10. <i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	192/3.0 mm	74.0	$n_D^{20.5}$ 1.6020	$C_{16}H_{20}O_2NBr$	56.7	5.6	56.8	5.9
11. <i>o</i> -Anisidine	185/1.0 mm	63.0	n_D^{20} 1.5750	$C_{17}H_{23}O_3N$	70.3	8.0	70.6	8.0
12. <i>p</i> - "	m.p. 90	60.6	—	"	70.5	7.8	"	"
13. <i>o</i> -Phenetidine	180/1.5 mm	88.4	n_D^{20} 1.5720	$C_{18}H_{25}O_3N$	71.2	8.1	71.3	8.3
14. <i>p</i> - "	190/1.5 mm	82.5	n_D^{20} 1.5665	"	71.3	8.1	"	"

TABLE 2—SUBSTITUTED 1,2,3,4-TETRAHYDROACRIDONES

Substituents	Reaction time min	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis			
					Found C	% H	Requires C	% H
1. 3,6-Dimethyl	6	310	66.1	$C_{15}H_{17}ON$	79.2	7.3	79.3	7.5
2. 3,6,7-Trimethyl	10	>300	74.7	$C_{16}H_{19}ON$	80.0	7.8	79.9	7.9
3. 3,6,8- "	15	"	66.4	"	79.6	7.6	"	"
4. 3-Methyl 8-chloro	"	279	72.6	$C_{14}H_{14}ONCl$	67.6	5.6	67.9	5.7
5. 3- " 6- "	6	>300	68.7	"	67.7	5.4	"	"
6. 3- " 6,8-dichloro	15	"	85.1	$C_{14}H_{13}ONCl_2$	59.6	4.5	59.6	4.6
7. 3- " 6-bromo	10	"	68.5	$C_{14}H_{11}ONBr$	57.3	4.6	57.5	4.8
8. 3- " 7,8-benz	15	"	76.0	$C_{18}H_{17}ON$	82.4	6.3	82.1	6.5
9. 3- " 5,6- "	11	"	83.7	"	82.0	6.4	"	"
10. 3- " 8-methoxy	10	278	65.8	$C_{15}H_{17}O_2N$	73.8	6.9	74.0	7.0
11. 3- " 6- "	6	>300	61.7	"	73.9	6.8	"	"
12. 3- " 8-ethoxy	10	212	70.0	$C_{16}H_{19}O_2N$	74.6	7.2	74.7	7.4
13. 3- " 6- "	10	307	85.6	"	74.6	7.1	"	"

IR γ_{max}^{Nujol} 1639 cm^{-1} for all compounds.

Substituted 1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydrophenanthridones

4-Methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxyanilide: A mixture of ethyl 4-methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate (1.84 g; 0.01 mol) and aniline (0.93 g; 0.01 mol) was heated at 180°-190° (oil bath) for 3 min. The cooled reaction mixture was extracted with ether, the ethereal layer extracted with aqueous sodium hydroxide (2%; 8×25 ml) and the solid obtained by acidifying the combined alkaline extracts with acetic acid was crystallised from benzene-pet. ether (60°-80°), had m. p. 115°. (Yield: 0.8 g; 34.6%).

(Found: C, 72.6; H, 7.2. C₁₄H₁₇O₂N requires C, 72.7; H, 7.4%).

Other anilides prepared in a similar manner are entered in Table 3. 4-Methyl cyclohex-1-one-2-anilide (0.46 g) dissolved in PPA [(phosphorus pentoxide (15 g) in orthophosphoric acid (10 ml)] protected from moisture was heated first on a water bath (1 hr) and then in an oil bath (140°-160°) for 15 min. The contents on cooling were poured over crushed ice with stirring, the deposited solid filtered, washed with water, dried and had m. p. 253°-4°, raised to 256° on crystallisation from ethanol (Yield: 0.35 g; 82.2%).

(Found: C, 78.6; H, 6.8. C₁₄H₁₅ON requires C, 78.9; H, 7.0%). IR $\gamma_{\max}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 1658 cm⁻¹ (>C=O of α -pyridone).

Other substituted phenanthridones prepared in an analogous manner are given in Table 4.

N-Aryl 5-methyl 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7-hexahydroindol-2-ones: A mixture of 4-methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-acetic acid (0.75 g; 0.0044 mol) and aniline (1.86 g; 0.02 mol) was refluxed in an oil bath at 200°-220° for 8 hr. The cooled reaction mixture was taken up in ether, the ethereal layer freed from the base by washing with dilute hydrochloric acid, washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄), ether recovered and the residual oil distilled in vacuum, b. p. 140°/2 mm. n_D^{28.5} 1.5465. (Yield: 0.65; 65%).

(Found: C, 79.1; H, 7.3. C₁₈H₁₇ON requires C, 79.3; H, 7.5%). IR $\gamma_{\max}^{\text{Neat}}$ 1715 cm⁻¹ (γ -lactam).

The other compounds prepared in a similar manner are entered in Table 5.

TABLE 3—4-METHYLCYCLOHEXAN-1-ONE-2-CARBOXYANILIDES

Name of the base	M. P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis			
				Found C	% H	Requires C	% H
1. <i>m</i> -Toluidine	126	40.8	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	73.4	7.6	73.5	7.8
2. 2,4-Dimethylaniline	274	44.4	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	74.0	8.2	74.1	8.1
3. 3,4-Dimethylaniline	115	38.6	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	74.0	8.2	74.1	8.1
4. <i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	132	46.4	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ NCl	63.1	5.8	63.3	6.0
5. <i>p</i> - " "	130	35.4	" "	63.2	6.0	" "	" "
6. α -Naphthylamine	187	50.0	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	76.8	6.6	76.9	6.8
7. β - " "	160	48.0	" "	76.8	6.7	" "	" "
8. 2,5-Dichloroaniline	158	41.7	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ NCl ₂	55.8	5.0	56.0	5.0
9. 2,4- " "	108	36.7	" "	55.7	5.1	" "	" "
10. <i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	105	30.6	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ NBr	54.4	5.1	54.2	5.2
11. <i>o</i> -Phenetidine	112	40.0	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	69.5	7.5	69.8	7.6
12. <i>p</i> - " "	127	36.4	" "	69.7	7.4	" "	" "
13. <i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	170	43.5	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂	60.6	5.7	60.9	5.8

Reaction time in each case was 5 min

TABLE 4—SUBSTITUTED 1,2,3,4-TETRAHYDROPHENANTHRIDONES

Substituents	M. P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis			
				Found C	% H	Requires C	% H
1. 2,7-Dimethyl	253	73.4	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ ON	79.1	7.6	79.3	7.5
2. 2,6,8-Trimethyl	267	69.2	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ON	79.6	7.7	79.7	7.9
3. 2-Methyl 8-chloro	190	74.7	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ ONCl	67.6	5.6	67.9	5.7
4. 2- " 6- " "	> 300	60.6	" "	67.7	5.6	" "	6.5
5. 2- " 7,8-benz	"	72.2	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON	81.9	6.4	82.1	6.5
6. 2- " 5,6- " "	303	68.4	" "	82.0	6.6	" "	6.6
7. 2- " 5,8-dichloro	256	76.8	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ ONCl ₂	59.5	4.4	59.6	4.6
8. 2- " 6,8- " "	245	70.9	" "	59.5	4.3	" "	4.8
9. 2- " 6-bromo	190	77.0	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ ONBr	57.4	4.8	57.5	4.8
10. 2- " 8-ethoxy	189	68.0	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	74.6	7.5	74.7	7.4
11. 2- " 6- " "	276	81.7	" "	74.5	7.3	" "	7.9
12. 2,6,7-Trimethyl	287	69.1	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ON	79.8	7.8	79.7	7.9

(a) Reaction time in each case was 15 min

(b) IR $\gamma_{\max}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 1658 cm⁻¹ for all compounds.

TABLE 5—*N*-ARYL 5-METHYL-2,3,4,5,6,7-HEXAHYDROINDOL-2-ONES

Arylamine	b.p. °C	Yield %	Refractive Index	Molecular formula	Analysis			
					Found C	% H	Requires C	% H
1. <i>p</i> -Toluidine	220/2 mm	60.2	$n_D^{25} 1.5535$	$C_{16}H_{19}ON$	79.4	7.8	79.7	7.9
2. 2,4-Xylidine	190/3 mm	58.0	$n_D^{25} 1.5545$	$C_{17}H_{21}ON$	79.7	8.3	80.0	8.2
3. <i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	200/2 mm	60.7	$n_D^{28} 1.5615$	$C_{15}H_{16}ONCl$	68.5	6.1	68.8	6.1
4. <i>o</i> -Anisidine	205/3 mm	66.1	$n_D^{25} 1.5635$	$C_{16}H_{19}O_2N$	74.5	7.5	74.7	7.4
5. <i>o</i> -Phenetidine	198/2.5 mm	58.6	$n_D^{25} 1.5565$	$C_{17}H_{21}O_2N$	75.1	7.8	75.3	7.7
6. <i>p</i> - „	m.p. 205	62.7	—	„	75.2	7.6	„	„
7. α -Naphthylamine	220/4 mm	61.5	$n_D^{25} 1.5645$	$C_{19}H_{19}ON$	82.0	6.7	82.3	6.9

References

1. A. KOTZ and B. MERKEL, *J. Pr. Chem.*, 1909, 79, 102; H. K. SEN and U. P. BASU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 309.
2. W. BUKHSH and R. D. DESAI, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1939, 10A, 262.
3. S. Z. AHMAD and R. D. DESAI, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1937, 5A, 543.
4. R. J. BROWN, F. W. S. CARVER and B. L. HOLLINGSWORTH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4295; 1962, 2624.
5. B. WITKOP, J. B. PATRICK and M. ROSENBLUM, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 2641.
6. S. S. BHARGAVA and G. S. SAHARIA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 284; 1972, 10, 919, 955.
7. G. S. SAHARIA and M. P. TYAGI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 1127; 1970, 47, 375.
8. A. BERTHO, *Angew Chem.*, 1955, 67, 515; *Chem. Ber.*, 1957, 90, 29.
9. R. MEYER, *Angew Chem.*, 1956, 68, 169.
10. G. S. SAHARIA and M. P. TYAGI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 936.
11. S. S. BHARGAVA and G. S. SAHARIA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 958.
12. A. BERTHO and H. KURZMANN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1957, 90, 2319.